

Acceleration of C/C++ Kernels and ONNX Models on CGRAs with MLIR-Based Compilation

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Abstract—Executing Artificial Intelligence (AI) at the edge is challenging due to tight energy and computational constraints. Heterogeneous platforms, particularly those incorporating Coarse-Grained Reconfigurable Arrays (CGRAs), offer a compelling trade-off between hardware specialization and programmability, supporting spatially distributed and energy-efficient computation. Despite their potential, the deployment of applications on CGRA accelerators remains limited by the lack of practical toolchains and methodologies. In this work, we propose a compilation flow based on MLIR to enable the seamless integration of both C/C++ kernels and ONNX-based AI models into a RISC-V system augmented with a CGRA accelerator. Our approach extracts the underlying Data Flow Graph (DFG) from the high-level representation. It maps it onto the CGRA using an Integer Linear Programming (ILP) mapper that accounts for the accelerator’s architectural constraints. A custom backend completes the toolchain by generating the necessary binaries for coordinated execution across the RISC-V processor and the CGRA. This framework enables the practical deployment of heterogeneous edge workloads, combining the flexibility of software execution with the efficiency of hardware acceleration.

Index Terms—RISC-V, CGRA, ONNX, Edge AI, MLIR

I. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of AI is driving the development of new applications across a wide range of domains, with a significant focus on edge use cases. New edge-oriented platforms such as NVIDIA’s Jetson series, Google’s Coral, or Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) based flows have gained prominence to support these applications. However, even more efficient execution of AI models is still necessary for greater scalability while reducing the increasing energy costs.

CGRAs are well-known but not widely adopted co-processor architectures, which are particularly adept at accelerating computations expressed as DFGs. They provide a compromise between dedicated hardware design, configurability, and the energy consumption of Graphics Processing Units (GPUs). In particular, when compared to these devices, literature reviews support that CGRAs may achieve a

superior performance-energy trade-off if properly exploited [1]. Offloading computations to CGRAs is often performed by targeting compute-intensive kernels written in C/C++. From the perspective of software programmers, some methods involve rewriting code with specific APIs, while others utilize custom compilers at the LLVM-IR level. Since computations are not explicitly represented as graphs, which CGRA mappers require as inputs, these approaches must identify loop-carried dependencies, nested operations, and partition the computation. However, at this level, the loss of context and semantic information hinders the exploitation of acceleration potential.

The Multi Level Intermediate Representation (MLIR) framework [2] is an open-source compiler infrastructure designed to support the definition and optimization of computations across multiple abstraction levels. It facilitates efficient transformations, analysis, and code generation for a wide range of hardware targets. Building on this capability, the central hypothesis of this work is that MLIR can effectively address the key challenges in supporting CGRA-based acceleration. Specifically, by preserving the high-level algorithmic structure and exposing parallelism of the applications, MLIR enables improved workload partitioning through the use of custom dialects and transformation passes tailored to the architectural characteristics of CGRAs.

Concurrently, the training and deployment of AI applications is supported by widely extended frameworks, such as PyTorch or TensorFlow, through specific backends to run the models. As part of this ecosystem, Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX) is an open format to represent already trained neural models (including the topology and weights) and is interoperable with other frameworks. It represents models as DFGs where each node is a high-level neural network operation, such as convolutions or ReLUs. Some approaches already exist to map ONNX to custom hardware, including CGRAs. However, this is typically done by converting the models to Low Level Virtual Machine (LLVM) or MLIR, thereby losing graph-level information, which must then be reconstructed [3]. Even so, domain-specific operations, e.g., ReLU, may be completely lost as they are converted to subroutines using conventional instructions.

In this work, we explore the use of MLIR to enhance the offloading of both C/C++ kernels and ONNX models to

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CGRAs for hardware acceleration. Our approach integrates a mapper based on ILP to optimize the deployment on STRELA [4], a spatially distributed CGRA developed in previous work. Specifically, for C/C++ code, we compile to MLIR and employ a custom dialect to extract DFGs, benefiting from existing optimization passes. For ONNX models, we implement a direct ONNX-to-DFG conversion that leverages the high-level semantic information available in the model structure. Both compilation paths converge into a unified intermediate representation, which is then consumed by a standard CGRA mapper and configuration manager, enabling streamlined deployment across heterogeneous workloads.

II. RELATED WORK

This section reviews the main existing frameworks for application mapping onto CGRAs, focusing on the three essential components for effective deployment: compilation, ONNX transformation, and mapping.

A. CGRA Compilation Frameworks

ML-CGRA [5] is an MLIR-based compilation approach for CGRAs. Authors assume a loose coupling and DMA capabilities for the CGRA, as well as king-mesh connection and buffers between Processing Elements (PEs). The units contain common operations for AI workloads, like *multiply-and-accumulate* and *max*. Models from PyTorch, TensorFlow, or ONNX are lowered to MLIR, and a pattern matching method identifies sequences of operations for acceleration and converts them to a *cgra-dialect*. For one benchmark AI model, the approach outperforms low-level LLVM-IR based mapping by $3.15\times$ on a 4×4 CGRA. However, the original model information is still lost by conversion to MLIR, and integration with a host processor is not addressed.

Morpher [3] is an open-source framework designed to explore and simulate CGRA designs. The flow relies on annotating loops in the source code. A custom LLVM pass extracts DFGs from these portions. The DFG generation addresses challenges like control divergence, recurrence edges, and predication. The experimental evaluation focuses on comparisons with previous state-of-the-art mappers, where Morpher shows comparable results in shorter mapping times. However, the flow requires manual partitioning of code by annotating target kernels; by relying on LLVM-IR, it suffers from the mentioned issues regarding information loss and host integration.

SO(DA)² (Software-Defined Architectures for Data Analytics) [6] introduces the *soda* dialect, which is used to partition input applications in LLVM-IR format, originating from C/C++ through Clang, or AI models converted to MLIR. Operations like loop flattening and unrolling are applied to the intermediate representations, followed by DFG generation and mapping. The mapper is a greedy process that stops at the first valid mapping for the lowest possible initiation interval. Through simulation via OpenCGRA [7], performance metrics are evaluated, design parameters are tuned, and the process is repeated until the target criteria are met.

B. ONNX Transformation Tools

`onnx-mlir` [8] is an LLVM-based project that lowers ONNX models into one of several MLIR dialects. This enables advanced optimizations through compiler passes and facilitates deployment on specialized hardware accelerators, such as GPUs and FPGAs. The lowering process in `onnx-mlir` decomposes complex ONNX operations into intermediate representations at the cost of losing the explicit graph structure and input data sizes.

`onnxruntime-web`¹ is a JavaScript library that extends the ONNX Runtime framework to enable ONNX model inference directly within web browsers. Leveraging WebAssembly (Wasm) and WebGL technologies for acceleration provides a lightweight and efficient environment for running machine learning models without needing a backend server. This client-side execution capability facilitates rapid prototyping and deploying interactive machine learning applications in web-based interfaces. While `onnxruntime-web` focuses on inference rather than model transformation, it demonstrates that ONNX models can target non-native contexts, highlighting the flexibility of the format and motivating the exploration of its use for contexts such as front-end for CGRA mapping.

`onnx2json`² is a Python library that converts ONNX models into a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) structure. By serializing the model’s structure, the conversion provides a means to manipulate the graph at a high level. The JSON format captures essential details such as nodes, edges, input and output specifications, and model metadata, enabling visualization and easier interfacing with other systems. We re-implement this parsing step in the approach proposed in this paper, extending its capability to retrieve information from the originating ONNX files.

C. CGRA Mappers

There are multiple ways to classify CGRAs, such as considering the memory architecture or connections between PEs [9]. Compilers are affected, in the first instance, by whether computation is spatially or temporally distributed throughout the CGRA. In this work, we target a CGRA for spatial computation. In the analysis carried out in [10], mapping for spatial CGRAs is divided into exact methods and approximate methods. Exact methods refer to ILP models, even though they may not always provide an optimal solution, and approximate methods include heuristic approaches, genetic algorithms, and simulated annealing. Additionally, techniques that utilize deep reinforcement learning have been tested in the literature [11].

III. COMPILING TO A RISC-V + CGRA SYSTEM WITH MLIR

In this work, we explore compilation methods to extract mappable DFGs from both C code and ONNX models, leveraging the MLIR framework in all cases to identify candidate code sections and generate the final binaries for the system.

¹<https://www.npmjs.com/package/onnxruntime-web>

²<https://github.com/PINTO0309/onnx2json>

Fig. 1. CGRA integration into the crossbar of the CVA6 Platform.

Fig. 2. Proposed flow show paths for conversion of C/C++ code (through MLIR) and ONNX models (through graph transformations) into CGRA configurations, and linking into RISC-V binary through MLIR ecosystem

The vast majority of CGRA implementations rely on generating such configuration words via dedicated tools. These configurations are then held in a local context memory of the CGRA [12]. This may result in lengthy runtimes for configuration generation, and in significant resource requirements regarding configuration memory sizes, as a function of the dimensions of CGRAs and the mapped DFGs. Furthermore, the use of the CGRA by a host processor is typically implemented through design-specific APIs or direct access to memory-mapped CGRA registers [13]–[16], which hinders the adoption of these accelerators due to the required source modifications.

Instead, we propose integrating the generation of CGRA configurations into a unified compilation flow, as shown in Figure 2. We explore two paths to arrive at mappable DFGs through MLIR, with the motivation that this ecosystem can provide our intended integrated compilation flow where a singular executable binary is produced for a RISC-V core containing the required CGRA control.

One compilation path accepts C/C++ code and is further explained in Section III-A, while the second targets ONNX models as inputs, as explained in Section III-B. In short, the C/C++ path uses the Polygeist [17] framework to generate MLIR code, and a custom transformation is then employed for DFG extraction. The second accepts models in ONNX format, i.e., graphs where each node represents very high-level operations, such as convolutions over tensors of arbitrary size, which we convert to DFGs, exposing the underlying operations. Both paths are intended to generate the same DFG format, which is suitable for use as input to the mapper

```
func.func @mac(%arg0: memref<?xi32>, %arg1: memref<?xi32>) ->
  ↪ i32 {
  %c0_i32 = arith.constant 0 : i32
  %0 = affine.for %arg2 = 0 to 100 iter_args(%arg3 = %c0_i32)
  ↪ -> (i32) {
  %1 = affine.load %arg0[%arg2] : memref<?xi32>
  %2 = affine.load %arg1[%arg2] : memref<?xi32>
  %3 = arith.muli %1, %2 : i32
  %4 = arith.addi %arg3, %3 : i32
  affine.yield %4 : i32
  }
  }
  return %0 : i32
}
```

(a) MLIR code generated by Polygeist for a C/C++ multiply and accumulate kernel

```
func.func @mac(%arg0: memref<?xi32>, %arg1: memref<?xi32>) ->
  ↪ i32 {
  %c0 = arith.constant 0 : index
  %c0_i32 = arith.constant 0 : i32
  "cgra.deploy" {
  %0 = vector.transfer_read %arg0[%c0], %c0_i32 :
    ↪ memref<100xi32>, vector<100xi32>
  %1 = vector.transfer_read %arg1[%c0], %c0_i32 :
    ↪ memref<100xi32>, vector<100xi32>
  %2 = arith.muli %0, %1 : vector<100xi32>
  %3 = vector.reduction <add>, %2 : vector<100xi32>
  ↪ into i32
  }
  }
  return %3 : i32
}
```

(b) code kernel transformed and identified with the partitioning dialect

Fig. 3. Example transformations for CGRA deployment from a C/C++ input

described in Section IV. We propose to convert the resulting mapping information (e.g., operation assignments to functional units, configuration time steps, etc.) into statements of an additional custom dialect that expresses these configuration steps. This dialect will be implemented by a respective custom RISC-V extension.

We consider our compilation target to be a RISC-V-based System-on-Chip (SoC) where a CGRA instance is used as the accelerator for AI workloads [18]. Summarily, the SoC is based on the CVA6 Development Platform [19], where we have integrated our custom memory-mapped CGRA, STRELA [4], as seen in Figure 1. The CGRA is composed of 16 PEs arranged in a 4×4 grid, each capable of performing 32 bit arithmetic, logical, and control operations, including branching for conditionals and loop constructs. Configuration is performed via 160 bit words that encode the operation and routing logic for each PE. These configuration words are derived from the mapping of a DFG onto the CGRA fabric.

A. MLIR Transformations for DFG Extraction from C/C++

The C/C++ input path relies on extracting candidate DFGs from textual MLIR representations. We have used Polygeist [17] to generate MLIR from conventional C/C++ code, with additional transformations that, after detecting and transforming patterns of operations that are available on the CGRA, encapsulate them for the following mapping step.

Figure 3a presents the MLIR generated from C source code using Polygeist. As this corresponds to standard MLIR, polyhedral optimizations can be applied at this stage. Figure 3b illustrates the use of a custom dialect to enable computation partitioning. In particular, the `cgra.deploy` scope encapsulates a multiply-and-accumulate operation, identified through pattern matching. The corresponding operations are further transformed into the standard `vector` dialect to facilitate memory streaming, which also enables the removal of the

affine.for loop through full unrolling. We are currently developing a dedicated compiler pass to refine and simplify the resulting DFG, minimizing visualization-related artifacts and isolating operations relevant to the CGRA mapping. This pass performs an analysis of indexing patterns to extract structural metadata, such as feedback dependencies, constants used in operations, array dimensions, and iteration counts. These parameters are then embedded into the DOT representation of the DFG to enrich each node with relevant execution details.

Regarding the use of ONNX models as inputs, `onnx-mlir` can generate input code similar to Figure 3a. Therefore, we initially explored this method to arrive at a common intermediate representation early for both C/C++ input and ONNX input, which could be subject to the same transformations and pattern matching. The `onnx-mlir` tool can generate the native `onnx` dialect or the commonly used upstream dialects like `arith` or `affine`. The issue regarding the former is that statements like `onnx.matmul` are too high-level for direct pattern matching into mappable code segments, as they implicitly represent N -dimensional loops containing multiple operations. For the latter, lowering to such dialects expands the implicit operations, but there is total information loss regarding the graph structure of the original ONNX model, including attributes like tensor sizes.

Therefore, to support ONNX models as inputs, we explore how to directly transform ONNX graphs to a DFG format. By making the DFG output from both input paths equivalent, mapping can be carried out directly with both methods in the same way, and any algorithm for spatial methods as described in the literature [10] may be used, as well as the proposed model in Section IV.

B. Converting ONNX Models to DFGs

The initial stage of the ONNX processing path involves converting models into DFGs by decomposing high-level operations into lower-level primitives. This functionality has been implemented in JavaScript/TypeScript and is illustrated in the bottom highlighted section of Figure 2. The process begins with parsing the ONNX model and initializing a DFG structure using `Cytoscape.js` [20], a robust library for graph manipulation and visualization. Within this representation, operations are systematically decomposed, optimization passes are applied, and a transformed ONNX graph is generated. The output remains a valid ONNX model, compatible with inference engines such as `onnxruntime-web`, allowing functional equivalence to be verified against the original model. Once the necessary transformations are complete, the model is further converted into a DFG format, specifically a DOT representation, compatible with the CGRA mapper proposed in this work. The subsequent sections detail the conversion process used to generate this DOT output.

1) *ONNX Model Parsing and JSON Conversion:* ONNX files represent trained AI models as computational graphs, where nodes correspond to high-level operations, such as matrix multiplications or convolutions, and inputs and outputs are typically N -dimensional tensors. However, as a binary

Fig. 4. Example conversion of (a) input ONNX containing a single `MatMul` node with implicit operations, into (b) a model with explicit element-wise operations (accesses to `A` and `B` are embedded in `Gather` and `Scatter` nodes) in a perfectly nested loop, and finally (c) conversion to DOT.

format designed for inference, ONNX is not directly suitable for structural manipulation. Since it is encoded using Protocol Buffers, it can be parsed using techniques similar to those employed by tools like `onnx2json`. While such tools focus on serialization, the implemented parser extends this functionality by decomposing high-level operations and translating them into an interactive graph format for visualization and analysis. The resulting structured JSON data captures the full topology of the model, including nodes, edges, and their attributes. It also retains key metadata for each node, such as operation type, input-output references, and tensor shapes. This representation provides a manipulable and transparent foundation for graph-based transformations. Using the generated JSON object, the initial Cytoscape graph is constructed without any loss of information from the original ONNX model.

2) *Cytoscape Graph Initialization:* After parsing, the model information is encapsulated within a Cytoscape graph object using a custom wrapper for the `Cytoscape.js` library. The graph's structure mirrors the original ONNX model. Three primary node types are defined: *Input and Output Nodes*, which correspond to the model's external interface and preserve variable names, data types, and tensor dimensions; *Operation Nodes*, which represent ONNX operators and include metadata describing their connected edges and the logical data flow; and *Edges*, which encode data dependencies between nodes and include placeholders for properties such as dimensions and data types.

Since intermediate tensors in ONNX graphs are not annotated with dimensional information, this metadata must be inferred. To this end, a recursive inference method is applied to compute and propagate tensor dimensions along the edges. The process begins from the operation nodes connected to the

output nodes, evaluating whether the dimensions of their input edges are known. If unknown, the associated parent operations are recursively examined, tracing upward through the graph until known input dimensions are found. At the conclusion of this stage, the resulting graph faithfully reproduces the original ONNX structure while explicitly annotating all intermediate tensor dimensions, facilitating subsequent transformation and analysis steps.

3) *Operation Decomposition*: Following graph initialization, each ONNX node is decomposed into primitive operations to ensure compatibility with graph-based mapping strategies. A library of transformation rules is defined to convert high-level operations into a sequence of elementary computational tasks. This process yields a transformed ONNX model that exposes explicit loop-level semantics, arithmetic and logical operations, and memory access patterns. To achieve this, constructs such as `Loop`, `Scatter`, and `Gather` are employed, along with nodes representing scalar computations. For instance, high-level nodes like `Add` or `MatMul`, which operate over N -dimensional tensors and abstract away loop iteration and memory access details, are systematically decomposed. The resulting representation replaces these nodes with explicit `Loop` structures containing element-wise operations. These include the management of loop iterators, evaluation of termination conditions, and calculation of memory access addresses, thereby exposing the underlying control flow and data dependencies required for downstream mapping onto hardware accelerators such as CGRAs.

As an example, Figure 4 shows the resulting expanded graph for an input matrix multiplication ONNX node. The implicit nested loops are extracted into a flattened loop, where index counters manage row and column traversal across matrices. Each iteration retrieves matrix elements, multiplies them, and accumulates the result in a designated output tensor position. Once again, specific tensor sizes allow for optimizing away the need for a loop. Other high-level ONNX operations are likewise transformed according to their computational structure. For example, element-wise operations are transformed into single loops, while tensor transformations like `Transpose` could be translated into data reordering tasks.

4) *Generation and Visualization*: After transformations are applied, the converted graph can be emitted as ONNX for functional validation or be rendered for interactive visualization. For mapping to the CGRA, a final conversion to an output DOT compliant with the mapper is performed. Figure 4c shows the DOT-based graph corresponding to the transformed model shown in Figure 4 in an intermediate stage of this conversion, where memory access operations must still be abstracted away, to match the execution model of the CGRA, where data is fed through pre-configured FIFOs to the PEs.

IV. MAPPING ONTO THE CGRA: USE CASE EXAMPLE

STRELA contains elastic PEs interconnected in a neighbor-to-neighbor topology. Each PE receives a configuration that remains stable until the computation of a new kernel, producing a spatial mapping in the CGRA that can compute any of

Fig. 5. Graph representing the inner connections of every PE

the DFGs presented in the previous sections. Due to the elastic logic they contain (i.e., buffers using producer/consumer handshakes, such as valid/ready interfaces), there is no need to balance the data paths of DFGs to ensure adequate data propagation. As no time-scheduling nor data path balancing (insertion of data bubbles) are needed, the features of this design are ideal for applying ILP optimization models to place and route DFGs into the fabric.

The mapping follows an ILP model based on [21], which is only suitable for kernels that fit entirely on the CGRA and are therefore referred to as one-shot kernels. It considers the DFG structure directly, assigning each DFG node operation to a PE and routes the corresponding node inputs and outputs. Many approaches make use of a Modulo Routing Resource Graph (MRRG) [22] to model the hardware architecture in modulo scheduling or ILP mapping. A MRRG takes into account elements such as multiplexers and registers, which enables timing control of the routing paths. However, due to the elastic logic we use, this architecture model is not necessary. Instead of following this approach, we have developed a higher-level mapper for simpler cases, and the only architectural features required are the connections shown in Figure 5.

To reduce the use of binary variables in the ILP problem, we do not consider each edge of the graph from Figure 5, but we use the input and output nodes that represent the ports, thus reducing from 20 variables to 8 in each PE.

The binary variables are, then:

- $FU_{m,n} = 1$ if operation n is mapped on FU_m .
- $R_{p,q} = 1$ if value q passes through port p .
- $R_{p,q,r} = 1$ if value q to r passes through port p .

Besides the standard constraints of operation placement and resource exclusivity ($\forall m, n, p$):

$$\sum_m FU_{m,n} = 1; \quad \sum_n FU_{m,n} \leq 1; \quad \sum_q R_{p,q} \leq 1$$

This approach considers the input and output nodes as functional units with additional constraints, such as $IO_{m,n} = R_{p,n}; \forall m \leq 4$ if p is one of the input nodes from the top. To ensure a fan-out continuity:

$$R_{p,q,r} \leq FU_{s,r} + \sum_{k \in \text{fanouts}(p)} R_{k,q,r}$$

Fig. 6. Example of multiple vector dot products from a `matmul` kernel with the extracted DFG and its mapping onto the CGRA. Inputs are at the top, and outputs are at the bottom.

$$FU_{m,n} \leq \sum_{p \in \text{fanouts}(m)} R_{p,q,r}; \forall q, r$$

With the term $FU_{s,r}$ only present for cases where p represents an input port. The number of PEs is minimized so that the unused ones can be power gated to reduce energy consumption. In order to minimize resources, the objective function is: $\min \sum R_{p,q}; \forall p, q$.

As a use case, the proposed optimization model has been applied to the matrix multiplication ONNX graph depicted in Figure 4. The corresponding mapping results, shown in Figure 6, demonstrate the feasibility of deploying this computation on the CGRA, highlighting how the model guides resource-aware scheduling and placement of operations.

V. CONCLUSION

This work presents an integrated compilation flow for RISC-V systems with a CGRA accelerator, supporting both C/C++ and ONNX inputs within a unified framework that includes a common mapping model and binary generation. By leveraging the MLIR infrastructure, CGRA configuration and invocation are embedded directly into the RISC-V binary, reducing integration complexity and eliminating the need for large configuration memories or explicit high-level APIs. This facilitates transparent computation offloading and supports the adoption of CGRA-based heterogeneous architectures for edge AI, even without specialized hardware knowledge. The approach emphasizes the importance of automated hardware-software partitioning and dynamic CGRA reconfiguration to support complex, multi-stage workloads.

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